

Activity Coefficients for Mixtures of Methylene Chloride with Benzene, Toluene, *o*-, *m*-, and *p*-Xylenes

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Activity coefficients for binary liquid mixtures with a common component (1) as methylene chloride and a varying component (2) as benzene, toluene, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-xylenes were calculated from free energy of mixing data and the values were fitted in two constant Margules equation. The infinite dilution activity coefficient values of the components were finally correlated with the carbon numbers of the varying component and the applicability of the correlations was discussed in terms of the existence of mobile liquid structures in these systems.

USUALLY the values of the component activity coefficients are greater than unity and indicate positive deviations from Raoult's law. However, a few classes of liquid mixtures do show values less than unity corresponding to the negative deviations¹ which are the result of weak specific interactions in such systems and much remains to be understood as yet about the systematics of the non-ideality. It was, therefore, considered desirable to calculate the activity coefficients for binary mixtures of methylene chloride with benzene, toluene, *o*-, *m*-, and *p*-xylenes which are known to possess weak specific interactions^{2,3} and to correlate the infinite dilution activity coefficients with structural parameters of the pure components.

Results and Discussion

Free energy of mixing G^E of a binary mixture with components 1 and 2 is related with corresponding component activity coefficients γ_1 and γ_2 respectively at temperature T and pressure P , by the equations⁴

$$R T \ln \gamma_1 = G^E + X_2 \left(\frac{\delta G^E}{\delta X_1} \right)_{T, P} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{and } R T \ln \gamma_2 = G^E - X_1 \left(\frac{\delta G^E}{\delta X_1} \right)_{T, P} \quad (2)$$

where X_1 and X_2 are the component mole fractions. In order to calculate the component activity coefficients from equations (1) and (2), the values of G^E for various compositions of the binary mixtures with component 1 as methylene chloride and component 2 as benzene, toluene, *o*-, *m*-, and *p*-xylenes were taken from the works of Nigam and Mahl². The values of $\left(\frac{\delta G^E}{\delta X_1} \right)_{T, P}$ were obtained

from G^E versus X_1 plots for suitable mole fractions covering the extreme dilute regions and the corresponding values of $\ln \gamma_1$ and $\ln \gamma_2$ were computed

and plotted against X_1 in each case (Fig. 1-A to 1-E).

It may be observed from Fig. 1-A to 1-E that for each binary mixture considered, the curves for $\ln \gamma_1$ and $\ln \gamma_2$ as functions of X_1 are of opposite slope and the gradients $\left(\frac{\delta \ln \gamma_1}{\delta X_1} \right)_{T, P}$ and $\left(\frac{\delta \ln \gamma_2}{\delta X_2} \right)_{T, P}$ are finite as X_1 and X_2 tend to zero respectively. Also, these curves approach to origin tangentially to the composition axis, i. e., $\left(\frac{\delta \ln \gamma_1}{\delta X_1} \right)_{T, P} \rightarrow 0$ as $X_1 \rightarrow 1$ and $\left(\frac{\delta \ln \gamma_2}{\delta X_2} \right)_{T, P} \rightarrow 0$ as $X_2 \rightarrow 1$.

Further, the values of

$$\left(\frac{\delta \ln \gamma_1}{\delta X_1} \right)_{T, P} \text{ and } \left(\frac{\delta \ln \gamma_2}{\delta X_2} \right)_{T, P}$$

were found to be consistent with the equation

$$X_1 \left(\frac{\delta \ln \gamma_1}{\delta X_1} \right)_{T, P} - X_2 \left(\frac{\delta \ln \gamma_2}{\delta X_2} \right)_{T, P} = 0 \quad (3)$$

within the limits of experimental error. These tests provide a check for the isothermal phase data of Nigam and Mahl².

In order to fit the activity coefficient data in two constant Margules equation

$$\ln \gamma_1 = (2A_{21} - A_{12})X_2^2 + 2(A_{12} - A_{21})X_2^3 \quad (4)$$

and

$$\ln \gamma_2 = (2A_{12} - A_{21})X_1^2 + 2(A_{21} - A_{12})X_1^3 \quad (5)$$

$\ln \gamma_1/X_2^2$ and $\ln \gamma_2/X_1^2$ were plotted as functions of X_2 and X_1 respectively in each case. The plots for a typical system are given in Fig. 2-A and 2-B.

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Fig. 1. Plots of $\ln \gamma$ vs X_1 for binary mixtures of

- (A) $\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2 + \text{C}_6\text{H}_6$,
- (B) $\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2 + \text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}_3$,
- (C) $\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2 + o\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{CH}_3)_2$,
- (D) $\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2 + m\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{CH}_3)_2$,
- and (E) $\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2 + p\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{CH}_3)_2$

Fig. 2. Plots of (A) $\ln \gamma_1/x_2^2$ vs. X_2 and (B) $\ln \gamma_2/x_1^2$ vs. X_1 for mixtures of methylene chloride with benzene.

As expected all these plots were straight lines and as such the constants A_{12} and A_{21} were calculated from the corresponding slopes and intercepts in each case. Further, for infinite dilution conditions equations (4) and (5) give

$$\ln \gamma_1^0 = A_{12} \quad \dots (6)$$

and

$$\ln \gamma_2^0 = A_{21} \quad \dots (7)$$

where $\ln \gamma_1^0$ and $\ln \gamma_2^0$ are the infinite dilution activity coefficients of components 1 and 2 respectively. The values of constants A_{12} and A_{21} as obtained from the curves similar to Fig. 2-A and 2-B for each system are compared with the corresponding values of $\ln \gamma_1^0$ and $\ln \gamma_2^0$ obtained from Fig. 1-A to 1-E in Table 1.

For the systems included in Table 1, the component 1 is fixed and the component 2 is varied by the substitution of $-\text{CH}_3$ group in benzene ring. If we consider the infinite dilution condition with $X_1 \rightarrow 0$ for such systems, the entire component 1 forms the solute species and the component 2 forms the solvent environment or the bulk. In such situation $\ln \gamma_1^0$ values may be correlated according to Black et al⁶ by the following equation

$$\ln \gamma_1^0 = K + (B/n_2)n_1 + F/n_2 \quad \dots (8)$$

where n_1 and n_2 are the carbon numbers of the components 1 and 2 respectively; while K , B and

TABLE I

VALUES OF A_{12} , A_{21} , $\ln \gamma_1^0$ AND $\ln \gamma_2^0$ FOR BINARY MIXTURES OF METHYLENE CHLORIDE WITH BENZENE, TOLUENE, *o*-, *m*-, AND *p*-XYLENES
Temp. = 20°

Sl. No.	System	A_{12}			$\ln \gamma_1^0$	A_{21}			$\ln \gamma_2^0$
		$\ln \gamma_1/X_2^2$ vs. X_2 plot	$\ln \gamma_2/X_1^2$ vs. X_1 plot	Average		$\ln \gamma_1/X_2^2$ vs. X_2 plot	$\ln \gamma_2/X_1^2$ vs. X_1 plot	Average	
1.	$\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2 + \text{C}_6\text{H}_6$	-0.110	-0.115	-0.1170	-0.117	-0.193	-0.192	-0.1925	-0.129
2.	$\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2 + \text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_3$	-0.140	-0.139	-0.1395	-0.142	-0.155	-0.149	-0.1520	-0.152
3.	$\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2 + o\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{CH}_3)_2$	-0.185	-0.191	-0.1880	-0.190	-0.201	-0.205	-0.2030	-0.200
4.	$\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2 + m\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{CH}_3)_2$	-0.160	-0.155	-0.1575	-0.163	-0.167	-0.160	-0.1635	-0.168
5.	$\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2 + p\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{CH}_3)_2$	-0.195	-0.190	-0.1925	-0.190	-0.206	-0.200	-0.2030	-0.200

F are homologous correlation constants. As the component 1 remains unchanged in each case, n_1 is constant and the above equation can be written as

$$\ln \gamma_1^0 = K + K'/n_2 \quad \dots (9)$$

where K' is equal to $(B n_1 + F)$. The constant K is a function of both the components 1 and 2, B is characteristic of the bulk which is formed by the varying component 2 when $X_1 \rightarrow 0$ and F is characteristic of its functional group.

Fig. 3. Plot of $\ln \gamma_1^0$ vs. $1/n_2$ for binary mixtures of CH_2Cl_2 with (a) C_6H_6 , (b) $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_3$, (c) $o\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{CH}_3)_2$, (d) $m\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{CH}_3)_2$ and (e) $p\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{CH}_3)_2$.

As required by equation (9), the plot of $\ln \gamma_1^0$ versus $1/n_2$ (Fig. 3) should be a straight line. It is obvious from Fig. 3 that the systems $[\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2 + \text{C}_6\text{H}_6]$, $[\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2 + \text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_3]$ and $[\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2 + m\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{CH}_3)_2]$ fall on a straight line; while the systems $[\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2 + o\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{CH}_3)_2]$ and $[\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2 + p\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{CH}_3)_2]$ show $\ln \gamma_1^0$ values higher than expected. If these are to fall on the same straight line, $o\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{CH}_3)_2$ and $p\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{CH}_3)_2$ both are to be assigned an effective carbon number equal to 10. Higher effective carbon numbers for $o\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{CH}_3)_2$ and $p\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{CH}_3)_2$ in comparison to $m\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{CH}_3)_2$ simply indicate that their solutions with CH_2Cl_2 are more non-ideal than that of

$m\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{CH}_3)_2$ with CH_2Cl_2 . This is expected because of the *o*-, *p*-, directing methyl group as substituent in the benzene ring which makes the second methyl group in these positions to contribute more towards non-ideality in comparison to the case where the second methyl group is in the *m*-position. It may be pointed out in this connection that effective carbon numbers have been assigned to take care of structural effects in other cases⁵ also.

On the other hand, if we consider these systems at the other extreme of infinite dilution with $X_1 \rightarrow 1$, the common component 1 forms the solvent environment or bulk and the entire component 2 forms the solute species. For such situations where the solvent environment is constant and solute species vary homogeneously, the following analytical expression is given by Black et al⁵

$$\ln \gamma_2^0 = K + B n_2 + C/n_2 \quad \dots (10)$$

where K again depends on component 1 and 2 both, B is characteristic of the solvent environment

Fig. 4. Plot of $n_2 [\ln \gamma_2^0 - K]$ versus n_2^2 for binary mixtures of CH_2Cl_2 with

- (a) C_6H_6 , (b) $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_3$, (c) $o\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{CH}_3)_2$, (d) $m\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{CH}_3)_2$ and (e) $p\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{CH}_3)_2$.

and C is characteristic of the functional group in varying component 2. Equation (10) for the systems considered here can be rearranged in the following form

$$n_2 [\ln \gamma_2^0 - K] = B n_2^2 + C \quad (11)$$

In order to test the validity of equation (11), as well as that of the assignment of effective carbon number for *o*-C₆H₄(CH₃)₂ and *p*-C₆H₄(CH₃)₂, in the systems under consideration, the value of K as determined from the intercept of the line in Fig. 3 was substituted in equation (11) and n₂[ln γ₂⁰-K] was plotted against n₂² in Fig. 4 which gave a fair straight line as required.

In this connection it may be pointed out that Black et al⁸ consider the component which tends to zero as the solute species. But this may not always be true in those systems where mobile liquid structures with one component of the binary mixture as the central and the other as the surrounding molecules are formed due to weak specific interactions as concluded from the mixture viscosity data⁸. Nevertheless, the fair applicability of equations (9) and (11) may be explained in the light of an earlier publication by the authors⁹. Their findings relevant for the purpose here are being given in Table 2.

It may be seen from Table 2 that for the infinite dilution situation with X₁→0 the components providing central as well as surrounding molecules in the mobile liquid structures and the component providing the bulk molecules for the binary mixtures considered are represented by columns III, IV and V respectively. A close scrutiny of column V reveals that the varying component 2 forms the bulk, while the common component 1 entirely remains in the form of mobile liquid structures. Though the liquid structures in each case are not similarly constituted, as is apparent from columns III and IV, yet the deviation in any response due to constitutional non-similarity in these mobile liquid structures becomes insignificant in comparison to the deviations produced by the extent of structuration due to the varying nature of the component forming the bulk

or solvent environment. This is so because the concentration of the liquid structures tends to zero as X₁→0. As such equation (9) correlates satisfactorily ln γ₁⁰ values with carbon numbers of the varying component alone which forms the bulk and any deviation from the requirements of equation (9) may thus justifiably be corrected by assigning an effective carbon number to only component 2 of a deviating system.

On the other hand, for the infinite dilution situation with X₁→1, the components providing the central and surrounding molecules in the solute species in the form of mobile liquid structures and the component providing the bulk or solvent environment are represented by columns VI, VII and VIII respectively. It is clear from column VIII that the common component 1 forms the bulk in each case. Obviously, the entire amount of the varying component 2 forms the solute species or the mobile liquid structures. In this case again as X₁→1, the concentration of the liquid structures tends to zero and as such the deviation in any response due to constitutional non-similarity of the liquid structures becomes insignificant in comparison to the deviation produced by the extent of structuration caused by the varying nature of component 2. This explains the applicability of equation (11) for correlation of ln γ₂⁰ with the carbon numbers of the varying component 2 in each case.

From the above, it is apparent that for the binary mixtures with one component common and the other varying homologically, the infinite dilution activity coefficients can satisfactorily be correlated with the carbon numbers of the varying component. However, in special cases, effective carbon numbers may be assigned to take care of special structural features and the structural non-similarity in the mobile liquid structures existing in the infinitely dilute binary mixtures produce insignificant deviation in comparison to that due to the extent of structuration caused by homologous structural variations in the varying component.

TABLE 2
CONSTITUENT COMPONENTS OF LIQUID STRUCTURES AND THE BULK IN BINARY LIQUID MIXTURES OF METHYLENE CHLORIDE WITH BENZENE, TOLUENE, *o*-, *m*- AND *p*-XYLENES

Sl. No.	System	Liquid Structures for 0 < X ₁ < 0.5			Liquid Structures for 0.5 < X ₁ < 1.0		
		Component providing central molecule (III)	Component providing surrounding molecule (IV)	Component providing bulk molecule (V)	Component providing central molecule (VI)	Component providing surrounding molecule (VII)	Component providing bulk molecule (VIII)
(I)	(II)						
1.	CH ₂ Cl ₂ + C ₆ H ₆	C ₆ H ₆	CH ₂ Cl ₂	C ₆ H ₆	C ₆ H ₆	CH ₂ Cl ₂	CH ₂ Cl ₂
2.	CH ₂ Cl ₂ + C ₆ H ₅ CH ₃	CH ₂ Cl ₂	C ₆ H ₅ CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅ CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅ CH ₃	CH ₂ Cl ₂	CH ₂ Cl ₂
3.	CH ₂ Cl ₂ + <i>o</i> -C ₆ H ₄ (CH ₃) ₂	<i>o</i> -C ₆ H ₄ (CH ₃) ₂	CH ₂ Cl ₂	<i>o</i> -C ₆ H ₄ (CH ₃) ₂	<i>o</i> -C ₆ H ₄ (CH ₃) ₂	CH ₂ Cl ₂	CH ₂ Cl ₂
4.	CH ₂ Cl ₂ + <i>m</i> -C ₆ H ₄ (CH ₃) ₂	CH ₂ Cl ₂	<i>m</i> -C ₆ H ₄ (CH ₃) ₂	<i>m</i> -C ₆ H ₄ (CH ₃) ₂	CH ₂ Cl ₂	<i>m</i> -C ₆ H ₄ (CH ₃) ₂	CH ₂ Cl ₂
5.	CH ₂ Cl ₂ + <i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ (CH ₃) ₂	CH ₂ Cl ₂	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ (CH ₃) ₂	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ (CH ₃) ₂	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ (CH ₃) ₂	CH ₂ Cl ₂	CH ₂ Cl ₂

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